

DIELECTRIC CONSTANTS OF INORGANIC SALTS

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Dielectric constants of several inorganic and metallic salts of organic acids have been determined and also their refractive indices. Correlation of the dielectric polarisation and molecular refraction to deformability of ions has been attempted.

A study of the dielectric constant (D.C.) of inorganic salts (non-metallic ionic solids) reveals many interesting points. The D.C. of non-metallic ionic solids arises from the shift of the charge as in non-polar molecular solids, but the shift of ionic charge which contributes to P_1 plays a more important part than the electronic effect.

The D.C. of the non-metallic ionic solids shows the following characteristics:—(i) The Maxwell's relation ($\epsilon \approx n^2$) does not hold good. (ii) Total polarisation and P_2 in ionic solids increases with increase in the size of ions. (iii) Solids having a close packing have high D.C. (Frank, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1937, 33, 513). (iv) A polymorphic substance has the highest D.C. in its densest form [e.g., Rutile (Density, 1.21; D.C., 114); Frank (*loc. cit.*)]. (v) The D.C. varies along the different axes of the crystal. (vi) Most of the solids (with a few exceptions) have D.C. less than 10.

Another characteristic property of the ionic salts is that their properties can be expressed in terms of the properties of the ions. In other words, the properties are additive. However, many cases have been recorded where deviation from the rule of additivity has been observed. Refraction of salts can be given as an example of this.

The colour of some halides also supports the above statement. Divalent lead ion and the iodide ion are both colourless but when both the ions combine a coloured lead salt is obtained. The colour of at least one of the ions must have changed under the influence of the other. Thus the proximity of one ion to the other creates a deformation in the other ion. The deformation of ions thus influences many other properties of the salts. Among such properties, the refractive index (molecular refraction) has been studied to a great extent by Fajans and Joos (*Z. Physik*, 1924, 23, 1; Fajans, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1927, 130, 724) and Fajans (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1928, 34, 502) has developed a theory known as the theory of deformation.

Fajans (*loc. cit.*) has correlated the departure of the molecular refraction from the additivity rule with the size of ions. The interionic distances in the inorganic salts do not obey the rule of additivity owing to the deformation of ions. Moreover, Fajans from a study of the properties and their departure from the additivity rule has been able to correlate these properties with the type of the valence bonds. It is not, however, possible to find the refractive index of many solids; hence to find a measure of the deformation, some other property of the solid must be studied. We thought that the determination of D.C. and polarisation may well serve as a measure of the deformation of the ions and also it may be interesting to see how the D.C. and polarisation are affected by the type of different linkages in the salts.

In the present work we have determined the D.C. of inorganic salts and metallic salts of organic acids with a view to correlating dielectric polarisation and molecular refraction to the deformability of the ions.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Purification of Salts.—All the salts used were of A.R. quality and were purified by crystallisation and obtained in the anhydrous form by fusion, if the salt did not decompose.

Solvents.—Xylene was dried over sodium and distilled. Nitrobenzene was fractionally distilled under reduced pressure.

Measurement of D.C.

Apparatus.—The apparatus used was the same as described by Bhide and Bhide (*J. Univ. Bom.*, 1938, 8, Part III, 93) and Gokhale, Phalnikar and Bhawe (*ibid.*, 1943, 11, Part V, 56).

Method of measuring D.C.—The D.C. of salts in the powder condition was measured by the mixture method. The mixture method was first introduced by Starke (*Wied. Ann.*, 1897, 69, 629) and Spater (*Ann. Physik*, 1902, 9, 919), and was further improved by Höjendahl (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1933, B 20, 54).

In this method the D.C. of the mixture of two pure liquids of various compositions were found at various temperatures. The liquids used must be such that the salts were insoluble in them. The D.C. of the mixture was determined systematically by varying the proportion of the mixture till the D.C. of the solid and the mixture was the same. This was known when the condenser had the same capacity with the liquid mixture in and also after introducing the powder in the liquid mixture.

Another way was to find a temperature—D.C. curve for the liquid mixture and on introducing the powder to find the curve of D.C. and temperature. The point of intersection of these two curves gives the value of the D.C. Care is taken to see that the powder is uniform and the condenser is dipped in the powder and air pockets excluded. This was achieved by keeping the solid in contact with the liquid for some time and shaking and applying a slight vacuum to remove the occluded air.

Measurement of Refractive Index

Molecular refractions of some solids were found out by measuring the refractive indices of their solutions using a Bausch and Lomb dipping refractometer and calculating the molar refractions by Hedestrand's formula (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1929, B 2, 428).

From Table I the following deductions can be made:—

(i) Densities of salts studied increase from the chloride to bromide and from bromide to iodide of an element. Iodides of lead, silver and cadmium (β) are exceptions to this rule, as they have densities lower than the corresponding bromides.

(ii) The dielectric constants of salts also follow the above order, *viz.*, $Cl < Br < I$. Potassium-chloride and potassium bromide have the same dielectric constant.

(iii) The molecular polarisation of iodide is greater than that of the bromide and of the bromide greater than that of the chloride of a metal. It will be noted that there is no exception to this generalisation. This is quite in accordance with the theory of deformation of Fajans. The size of ions increases from Cl to Br and Br to I. Therefore, the deformability increases. The polarisation depends on the deformability of the ion. This gives an explanation of the increase in dielectric polarisation from Cl to Br and from Br to I of a metal.

(iv) The polarisations of potassium and silver salts (Table II) are nearly the same. This will be referred to later.

(v) The density and dielectric constant of the polymorphic forms of HgI_2 and CdI_2 have also been given in the table. The polymorphic forms have different densities and dielectric constants and also different molecular polarisations. HgI_2 (yellow) has a higher polarisation (64.31) than the red variety (58.97) and CdI_2 (β) has a higher polarisation (70.06) than the α -form (56.66).

TABLE I

Substance.	Density.	Dielectric constant			
		Present work.	Previous values.	Molecular polarisation.	Molecular refraction.
NaCl	2.161	6.29	6.26 ³ 5.61 ¹ 6.28 ⁹ 5.81 ⁶ 6.12 ⁶ 5.81 ¹ 9.3 ² 5.83 ^{1b}	17.26	8.52
NaBr	3.203	6.45	6.11 ¹	20.72	13.17
NaI	3.655	7.17	6.15 ¹¹	34.74	19.74
KCl	1.985	5.00	4.85 ⁹ 4.79 ⁹ 4.54 ¹² 3.97 ¹² 4.51 ¹⁷ 2.42 ¹⁶ 4.75 ⁴ 5.03 ⁶ 2.4 ³ 4.94 ³ 4.81 ⁶ 4.64 ¹⁶	21.46	10.85
KBr	2.749	4.94	4.7 ⁹ 4.61 ¹ 4.67	24.58	13.98
KI	3.12	7.00	5.21 ¹¹ 5.6 ⁹ 5.27 5.17 ¹²	35.57	20.73
AgCl	5.502	14.13	10.9 ⁹ 11.27	21.21	13.43
AgBr	6.245	15.09	12.1 ⁹ 12.27	24.79	16.70
AgI	5.644	33.86	...	37.92	23.25
BaCl ₂	3.923	8.42	11.44 ⁹	37.9	22.3
BaBr ₂	4.575	8.66	12 ⁹	46.5	28.7
CaCl ₂	2.150	5.85	...	31.9	18.75
CaBr ₂	3.350	6.15	...	37.71	25.75
MgCl ₂	2.320	4.42	...	21.87	17.69
MgBr ₂	3.720	4.96	...	28.17	14.69
PbCl ₂	5.912	39.06	42 ⁹ 33.5 ¹³ 25.06 ¹⁷ 6.03 ¹⁰ 4.6 ⁸ 4.2 ⁸ 6 ⁸	43.61	26.63

TABLE I (contd.)

Substance.	Density.	Present work.	Previous values.	Molecular polarisation.	Molecular refraction
PbBr ₂	6.648	42.6	42 ^a , 49 ^b	51.50	33.62
PbI ₂	6.078	113	113 ^a 24 ^b	74.53	47.94
HgCl ₂	5.435	8.17	2.95 ¹⁰ 3.2 ^b	35.22	22.45
HgBr ₂	6.035	9.84	...	44.60	29.45
HgI ₂ (red)	7.070	34.32	...	58.97	42.05
(yellow)	6.282	25	...	64.31	...
CdCl ₂	4.047	6.73	...	39.73	10.29
CdBr ₂	5.192	7.32	...	34.24	13.03
CdI ₂ (α)	5.670	22.5	...	56.66	20.3
(β)	4.660	25.6	...	70.08	...
FeCl ₂	2.482	5.8	...	31.45	...
Na-acetate	1.518	4.44	...	28.83	14.52
K-acetate	1.815	5.56	...	32.61	16.85
Ag "	3.260	6.25	...	32.58	...
Ba "	2.424	5.44	...	48.35	24.82
Ca "	1.509	4.66	...	36.03	...
Pb "	3.12	7.79	...	59.17	35.41
Hg "	3.270	4.82	...	54.61	...
Cd "	2.194	5.11	...	60.72	...
Zn "	1.745	4.52	...	56.72	...
K ₃ Fe(CN) ₆	1.822	6.24	...	114.91	...
K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆	1.886	14.4	...	160.66	...

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17. F. Keller and Lechmann, *Z. Physik.*, 1913, 677.
18. Burton and Turnbull, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1937, 188, A, 182.

A few more interesting facts can be observed from the molecular polarisations of these salts. Table III gives the difference between the polarisations of a bromide and a chloride and that of an iodide and a bromide of an element.

TABLE II

Substance.	Chloride.	Bromide.	Iodide.	Acetate.
Potassium	21.45	24.57	35.57	32.61
Silver	21.21	24.79	37.92	32.58

TABLE III

Differences in dielectric polarisation between iodides and bromides and bromides and chlorides of salts.

Element.	MBr-MCl.	Diff. from the mean 3.4.	MI-MBr.	Element.	$\frac{1}{2}(MI_2-MBr_2)$.	Diff. from the mean 3.4.	
Lithium*	3.67	0.27	4.01	Magnesium	3.15	-0.25	—
Sodium	3.46	0.06	14.0	Calcium	2.9	-0.5	—
Potassium	3.14	-0.26	10.89	Barium	4.3	0.9	—
Silver	3.58	0.18	13.1	Cadmium	2.3	-1.1	(a) form 11.2
				Mercury	4.5	1.1	yellow form 9.85
				Lead	3.9	0.5	11.5

* Stenlmann, *Z. Physik*, 1932, 77, 114 and Schupp, *Z. Physik*, 1932, 78, 83.

TABLE IV

Element.	$M(C_2H_3O_2)$ -MCl.
Sodium	11.57
Potassium	11.17
Silver	11.37
Barium	5.39
Mercury	9.7
Calcium	2.09
Cadmium	15.5
Lead	7.78

TABLE V

Element.	Chloride.	Bromide.	Iodide.
Sodium	2.02	1.57	1.76
Potassium	1.98	1.76	1.62
Silver	1.59	1.49	1.63
Magnesium	1.24	1.14	—
Calcium	1.7	1.45	—
Barium	1.7	1.62	—
Cadmium	2.89	2.46	2.79
Mercury	1.57	1.51	1.53
Lead	1.64	1.53	1.55

It will be observed that the differences between the polarisations of the bromide and chloride (MBr—MCl) are nearly 3.4 which is the mean of the differences of all the salts given in the above table with the exception of barium, cadmium and mercury. As will be shown later that in the case of mercury and cadmium and to a certain extent in the case of lead this irregularity is to be expected. The rest of the salts therefore show that there is an additive relationship in the dielectric polarisation of the bromides and chlorides. The difference in the polarisation of the corresponding iodides and bromides do not show this regularity to any marked extent. This additive relationship is therefore not observed with iodides. This may be due to greater deformation possible in the case of the iodine ion (Fajans, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1941, 9, 282). The case of barium appears to be an exception.

The additive relationship is also seen in the case of alkali acetates and chlorides of metals. The differences in the polarisations of acetates and chlorides of metals are given in Table IV.

It will be seen that in the case of monovalent salts, *i.e.*, in the case of sodium, potassium and silver, the differences are surprisingly the same while in the case of bivalent salts examined, no such relationship is observed.

In Table V the ratios of the dielectric polarisations to molecular refractions of salts are given.

It will be observed that the ratio is always less in the case of bromide than in the chloride with the exception of K. This ratio is of the order : Cl > Br < I.

From the above observations it will be seen that salts which have a definite ionic structure show certain regularity in their physical properties such as density, dielectric constants, dielectric polarisations, etc., while AgI, PbI₂, HgI₂, and CdI₂, show considerable departure from these regularities.

The structures of these salts will now be discussed in the light of experimental and theoretical data other than dielectric polarisation.

These salts are coloured ; moreover PbI₂, MgI₂, and CdI₂ have layer lattice while AgI shows an ionic lattice. The atomic distances in these salts are considerably less than those required for ionic substances.

The diamagnetism of CdBr₂, CdI₂, and ZnI₂ have been examined by Subramanian (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1936, **4A**, 404). He finds that there is a considerable increase in magnetic susceptibilities of these salts in solution. Ionic solids like KCl do not show this behaviour. The increase in susceptibility in solution is attributed to the change in the linkage due to the interaction of the solvent. CdI₂ and ZnI₂ are supposed to be partially co-valent in the solid condition and on solution they are split up into ions due to a loosening of the bond by the action of the solvent. In the case of HgCl₂, there is no such change on solution. This is regarded as an exception.

Tables VI and VII give the lattice energies and the observed and calculated ionic distances in the case of silver halides.

TABLE VI

*Lattice energy.**

Salts.	Obs.	Calc.	Difference.
AgCl	213.9	203	11.9
AgBr	210.9	197	13.9
AgI	208.2	190	18.2

TABLE VII

Ionic distances.

Salt.	Ionic.	Co-valent	Obs.	Difference.
AgCl	3.07	2.52	2.77	0.30
AgBr	3.21	2.64	2.88	0.33
AgI	3.42	2.81	2.99	
	3.28	2.81	2.80	0.48

It will be seen that the deviation from the observed anion-cation distances and the calculated ionic distance becomes progressively more pronounced as we pass from chloride to bromide and iodide. Likewise the difference between experimental and theoretical lattice energies become progressively greater. Moreover, AgCl and AgBr have NaCl type of lattice whereas AgI has a tetrahedral type of lattice, which is recognised as a characteristic of co-valent linkage. This type of lattice is of course to be expected with ionic linkage if the ratio of cation : anion radii is small enough ; but the ratio is not

* Mayer, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1933, **1**, 327, .270 ; Mayer and Levy, *ibid.*, 1933, **1**, 647.

small in the case of AgI. In addition it is believed that the increasing insolubility of Ag salts is directly connected with an increasing co-valent character. The size of the Ag ion is only slightly smaller than that of K. This explains the close parallelism between the polarisation of Ag and K salts (Table II).

To summarise, the evidence of AgI being regarded as partly co-valent is (i) crystal form (tetrahedral), (ii) increase in difference between observed and calculated lattice energies, (iii) increase in difference between observed and calculated ionic distances. The only point in favour of regarding AgI as ionic is its electrical conductivity in the solid condition. Therefore we may conclude that the linkage between Ag and I is of the transition type, *i.e.*, between electro-valent and co-valent.

The following tables (VIII and IX) give the lattice energies observed and calculated, and ionic distance of PbI_2 and CdI_2 respectively.

TABLE VIII

*Lattice energy.**

Salt.	Obs.	Calc.	Difference.
PbI_2	497.1	457.7	39.4
CdI_2	563.1	473.6	89.5

TABLE IX

Ionic distances.

Salt.	Obs.	Ionic.	Covalent.
$CdCl_2$	2.66	2.59	2.47
CdI_2	2.99	2.95	2.76

The crystal form of CdI_2 is a remarkable mixture of molecular, non-polar and ionic forces, the crystal consisting of layers. Each layer consists of three planes—one of Cd atom surrounded on either side by a plane of equal number of iodine ions. The molecules are thus held together mostly by Van der Waal's forces. This is quite unlike ionic crystals.

Table X gives the observed internuclear distances for Hg salts.

TABLE X

Ionic distances.

Salt.	Obs.	Ionic.	Co-valent.
$HgCl_2$	2.25	2.43	2.47
$HgBr_2$	2.48	2.56	2.12
HgI_2	2.78	2.98	2.76

TABLE XI

Salt.	Dielectric constant.	Dielectric polarisation.
AgI	33.86	37.92
HgI_2 (red)	34.32	58.97
HgI_2 (yellow)	25	64.31
PbI_2	113	74.53
CdI_2 (α)	22.5	56.66
CdI_2 (β)	25.6	70.08

In the case of HgI_2 the observed distance (2.78) is very close to the distance required for a co-valent linkage (2.76) while that for the ionic linking amounts to 2.98.

From the above it will be seen that HgI_2 , AgI, PbI_2 and CdI_2 have definitely an intermediate type of linkage. The salts show abnormally high dielectric constants ϵ_n

* The values of lattice energies for CdI_2 and PbI_2 are taken from the calculations of Sherman (*Chem. Rev.*, 1932, 14, 93). These values are not very accurate but the difference in the calculated and observed values of lattice energies is sufficiently large and from what has been said about AgI it will be clear that CdI_2 and PbI_2 are predominantly co-valent (Fitzer and Hildebrand, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 2472). They have discussed the relationship of colour and bond character and are of opinion that AgI and CdI_2 are partially ionic.

high dielectric polarisation. Ionic salts possess generally a dielectric constant varying between 5 and 10. Table XI illustrates this point.

The dielectric constant of ferrous chloride is 5.8, nearly of the same order as shown by the ionic type of crystals. Therefore FeCl_2 belong definitely to the compounds of the electro-valent type. It was intended to find the dielectric constant of ferric chloride; which is known to have a co-valent linkage. But the compound is soluble in organic solvents used and hence its dielectric constant could not be determined.

The dielectric constants of potassium ferricyanide and potassium ferrocyanide were determined with a view to finding out the effect of complex ions on the dielectric constants of the salts. The dielectric constants of these salts are: $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$, 6.24; $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$, 14.4.

The dielectric constants are comparatively low and thus these salts resemble other ionic salts. Errera and Bresseur (*Phys. Z.*, 1933, 34, 369) have determined the dielectric constants of calcium, strontium, magnesium and barium platinocyanides. The dielectric constants of these salts range from 5 to 9 showing that these salts also belong to the ionic type.

The molecular refractions of acetates in acetic acid could be determined only for those of sodium, potassium, barium and lead as these were the only acetates soluble in acetic acid. The data, however, are incomplete for a detailed comparison. The ratios of the dielectric polarisation to molecular refractions of these acetates are given below.

TABLE XI

Salt.	Dielectric polarisation.	Molecular refraction.	Ratio.
Na-acetate	28.83	14.516	1.986
K-acetate	32.61	16.830	1.936
Ba-acetate	48.35	24.816	1.930
Pb-acetate	59.18	35.409	1.672

It will be seen that in the case of sodium, potassium and barium acetates the ratio is nearly 2, which is also found in the case of the corresponding ratio of sodium and potassium chlorides. The interpretation of these results on other lines is being carried out by one of us (N. V. S.) with Dr. S. K. K. Jatkar and will be published in another paper.

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